

CONCEPT OF PRĀṆA AND PRĀṆĀYĀMA IN TRI-SHIKI-BRAHMANA UPANISHAD

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Abstract

Aim and Objectives: The present study was conducted to explore and elucidate the origin and functioning of Prana and the rules and regulations, techniques, and consequences of Pranayama in Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishads.

Introduction: Prana and Pranayama are the integral component of Yoga but, both are interlinked to each other. Prana is the vital force whereas Pranayama is the practice to control and expansion of the vital force. The Tri-Shiki-Brahmana is one of the twenty Yoga-Upanishads and forms part of the Sukla-yajur-veda Upanishad. It elaborates various Yogic concepts such as Jnana Yoga, Prana, Astanga Yoga, and Brahman.

Methods: The Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishad listed in the Muktika Upanishad were included in this study. All the Original verses written in Sanskrit were translated into English for literal and unambiguous interpretation of the concepts of Prana and Pranayama.

Discussion: According to this Upanishad, after mastery over the Yamas, Niyamas and Asanas and after the purification of Nadis, should start the Pranayama and by acquiring the knowledge Nadis and vayus, exert in the Purification Nadis.

Conclusion: The Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Comprehensively describes the evolution, position, functioning, and course of Prana and the rules, procedure, outcomes, and destruction of diseases through Pranayama were explained as the fourth step of Astanga Yoga.

Keywords:

Prāṇa, Prāṇāyāma, Vayus, Nadis, Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishad

INTRODUCTION

Prana is a Sanskrit root word, which is literally mean the vital force, macrocosmic and microcosmic, and is the substratum of all life energy behind all things and beings in the universe. In Atharva Veda, Prana is the hard-core of all creation which breathes and breathes not. This characteristic of prana indicates it's all pervasiveness and it also explains the movement of prana lead to jiva's identification with the gross body ^[1]. Traditionally, one's direct experience with the Prana plays a prominent role in understanding and defining this concept. Practice or applications of Prana have many facets like, to heal, to achieve Siddhis, and to understand and reach the Brahman ^[2]. According to Prasna Upanishad, Prana and Food are two entities which are the root cause of the creation in multifarious ways. It also defines the is verily Prana and Food is verily the Moon ^[3].

The word Pranayama is derived from two Sanskrit root words Prana means Vital force and the word Ayama mean to gain control. Maharshi Patanjali defines Pranayama as 'The regulation of the movements of inhalation and exhalation'. He also states that by the practice of Pranayama, the darkness that hides the light of wisdom is destroyed and is regulated by place, time and number meaning that at various times in our Yoga Sadhana ^[4]. The Yoga Upanishads defines Pranayama is expiration (Rechaka) of impure from the body, then inspiration (Puraka) of pure air, then purifying the air by holding (kumbhaka), similarly holding after complete exhalation. These four processes are said to be pranayama ^[5].

The Tri-shiki-Brahmana Upanishad is the forty fourth of the 108 Upanishads and forms the part of Sukla Yajurveda and it is one of the twenty Yoga Upanishads ^[6]. It is the conversation between

a Brahmana named Tri-shikhi (three thufths) and Surya, the sun god, who explains to the former the distinction between the body and the soul and the means to achieve kaivalya or liberation ^[7]. It describes about the Brahman and Pinda, pancha Mahabhutas and its varients, eight folded yoga path and brief explanation about the eight angas, the concept of Prana and other vayus with their location and function, Nadis and their location, the process of purification of nadis, the concept of Pranayama such as, rules and regulation, definition, procedure, Benefits, Destruction of disease through the regular regular Practice of Pranayama, and prediction of death through the movement of prana in various parts of the body and Meditation on the Saguna and Nirguna Brahman.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The present study was conducted to explore and elucidate the origin and functioning of Prana and the rules and regulations, techniques, and consequences of Pranayama in Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishads. To identify and elaborate the various Nadis and the course of Prana, which awaken the kundalini.

METHODS

The Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishad listed in the Muktika Upanishad were included in this study. All the Original verses written in Sanskrit were translated into English for literal and unambiguous interpretation of the concepts of Prana and Pranayama.

DISCUSSION

Evolution of Prana:

According to the Tri-Shiki-Brahmana Upanishad, the Body, Prana, the Cause and the Atman is everything of Shiva. Who, is the Supreme Being, absolute bliss, pure, and eternal. It explains the evolution of the Universe or Creation. From Brahman, Avyakta came into existence. From Avyakta, Mahat came into existence. From Mahat, Ahamkara came into existence. Out of Ahamkara, five Tanmatras came into existence. From Tanmatras, Pancha Mahabhutas came. From Mahabhutas, the entire world came into existence. Of the Mahabhutas, from Vayu, Prana is one of the five variants. It also given that the function of the Prana is breathing. By identifying himself with the knowledge of all the divisions and the evolution is the Jiva. Then the Pancha-karna of the Five elements Expound. Ahamkara (Self-consciousness) along with Prana, through the nose, having the quality of smell and dependent on anus takes abode in Prithvi. Thus, the creation starts with Brahman and ends with Panchi-Karana.

Rules to Pranayama

Having practiced and got mastery over Yama, Niyama, Asana, and purification of Nadis one should practice Pranayama. It mentioned the height of one's body which is ninety-six Angulas when measured with his thumb and Prana is one-hundred-eight Angulas height. By the practice of yoga, one can reduce the length of Prana by generating the Agni. He is the knower of Brahman. A twelve spoked chakra is there in the region of fire and the Jiva twirls around the wheel, one spoke after other, hanging on Prana. like spider balances itself in the middle of the cob-web.

Concept of Kundalini

Awakening the Kundalini with the practice of Pranayama is one the path to attain the knowledge of Brahman. So, in this Upanishad describes the kundalini, which is above the navel in a horizontal line. It is composed of eight different constituents and is a spiral of eight coils. It regulates Prana, Apana and the onward passage of water and food. It has an orifice that leads to the Brahmarandhra. While practicing yoga, it shines in the ether of heart in the form of a serpent when aroused by Agni and Prana.

Nadis and Vayus:

By knowing the differences, position and functions of the Nadis and Vayus, the practioner will endeavour towards the purification of Nadis. Two Angulas above the seat of Apana and below the seat of genitals in the middle of the body for men. It is surrounded by several Nadis, nearly eighty-thousand

Nadis. Among them, Susumna is firmly established. It is placed inside in the middle of the umbilical knot extends straight up to Brahmarandhra. Nadis, Ida and Pingala stand at the left and right of Susumna and terminates at the left and right nostrils. Gandhari and Hasti-Jihva stand at the front and rear side of Susumna terminate at the left and right eyes. Pusa and Yasasvini terminate at the left and right ears. Alambusa terminates at the anus. Subha Nadi extends up to the tip of the genitals. Kausiki to big toes.

According to this Upanishad, Prana is most the important of two Vayus, which are important of the first five important Vayus among the ten Vayus because it carries Jiva. The Prana pervades middle of the mouth, nose, heart, and navel. Apana in the anus, genitals, thighs, and knees. Samana in the whole body. Udana in the joints of the legs and hands. Vyana in the two arms, thighs, hip, ankles, shoulders, and throat. The other five Vayus are placed in the skins, bones, and other parts of the body. The water, food, and other liquids are assimilated in the stomach. The Prana separates them into various constituents. The Apana evacuates wastewater and food. The actions of Prana and Apana are done by Vyana. Anything that remained in the body is raised up by Udana. Samana does the work of nourishment to the body. Naga performs belching. Kurma opening and closing of the eyes. Krikara functions for eyes. Devadatta does the work of seep. Dhananjaya performs the work of swelling and even after death.

Place and Time

The yogi should choose a secluded spot for practice. The width of the seat should be twice the height and should be covered with Darbha, Kusa-grass and the skin of a black antelope. Having comfort in his Asana like Swastika Asana. He should practice up to eighty Kumbhakas at a time, four times daily at dawn, mid-day, evening, and midnight.

Techniques of Pranayama

By assuming his Asana, one should keep the body erect, mind alert and at ease, with his eyes fixed on the tip of the nose, teeth not touching the other row of teeth, tongue fixed to the palate, with his head slightly inclined downwards, with his hands in Chin-mudra, one should begin Pranayama. According to this Upanishad, Expiration, Inspiration, Retention, and expiration are the four processes of Pranayama. The yogi should exhale through the pingala. Then inhale through the left nostril for sixteen matras, retain for a count of sixty-four Matras and exhale through the right nostril for thirty-two matras. The process should be repeated again and again in the reverse and direct order. That means after exhaling through the right nostril, he should inhale through the same nostril and repeat the process.

Symptoms of Pranayama Siddhi

He who experiences profuse sweat is of an inferior type. For him, all sins and ailments are destroyed. He who experiences a tremor of the body is of medium type. For him, all sins, ailments, and incurable diseases are destroyed. He who experiences levitation is of a superior type. He will have a light body, passing small urine, and evacuate small fecal matter, light body, moderate food, ever alert sense organs and intellect over vision of past, present, and future.

Destruction of Disease

The yogi should project his prana and mind to the points of the knot of the navel, the tip of the nose, and big toes by practice at Sandhyas. Then he will get rid of the clutches of all diseases and fatigue. By Dharana on the navel, all diseases of the belly are cured. On the tip of the nose, longevity and lightness of the body are gained. He who drinks the air for three months is bestowed with great power of speech. Six months of practice will bestow him with the destruction of great disorders.

Knowing life span through the course of Prana

Controlling the vital air through the practice at sandhyas and so on the yogi can observe the signs of vibrations at his limbs and he can predict even his time of death. If throbbing ceases at his big toes of feet and thumbs of hands, his life is assured for at least one year. In the ankles and wrist, is only six months. In the elbow, is only three months. In the armpits and lateral part of genitals, is one month. Any good signs are seen, half-a-month is the time. In the belly, it is ten days. If he sees radiance like

fire-fly, five days. If he could not see the tip of the tongue, he will survive for three days. If this symptom is observed when a flame is seen, he can count two days. Knowing his lifetime by observing the above signs, go for his final prayer, meditation for the attainment of the final merger with Paramatman.

CONCLUSION

According to the Tri-Shiki-Brahmana, By Yoga, Jnana is developed. By Jnana, yoga is further developed. A yogi who has the course of yoga and Jnana together and he should practice the Astanga yoga. In this eight-fold path Pranyama is fourth stage. It Comprehensively describes the evolution of Prana, Rules to Practice Pranayama, the concepts like Kundalini, Nadis and Vayus are related to the Practice of Pranayama. So, these three concepts were explained with the position and functioning. It elaborated the place, time, procedure, symptoms of Pranayama siddhi, destruction of diseases the Practice of Pranayama in well controlled manner at all the sandhyas. But it does not describe the types of Pranayama.

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